

19 Abstract

20 Phenolic compounds are a minor constituent of virgin olive oil (VOO), and their unique profile
21 within a particular VOO significantly depends on the olive cultivar. These compounds largely
22 contribute to the nutraceutical properties of VOO, the organoleptic attributes and the shelf life due to
23 their antioxidant capabilities. Malaxation is a central step in the oil extraction process, consisting of
24 mixing the olive paste to induce the formation of a continuous lipid phase. The effects of malaxation
25 conditions on the VOO phenolic profile, as well as the relative contribution of specific phenolic
26 compounds to the oxidative stability of the product, have been scarcely studied. We contributed to
27 these topics in the following ways: first, we tested the effects of different malaxation times on the
28 concentrations of nine relevant phenolic compounds, and second, we evaluated the influence of
29 performing malaxation under vacuum. We included VOOs from eight olive cultivars with contrasting
30 phenolic profiles in these tests. An increase in malaxation time significantly decreased the
31 concentrations of aglycon isomers of oleuropein and ligstroside but, conversely, increased the
32 oleocanthal and oleacein contents. In addition, malaxation under vacuum led to an increase in
33 phenolic contents compared to standard conditions carried out at atmospheric pressure. Additionally,
34 the genotype had a strong influence in this context. Finally, we explored the possibility of predicting
35 the VOO shelf life on the basis of the phenolic profile. The oxidative stability of the VOOs was
36 estimated by the Rancimat method, and a predictive model was developed by combining the
37 concentration of the VOO phenolic compounds and the main fatty acids. The high predictive capacity
38 of the model ($R^2 = 0.923$; $p < 0.0001$) emphasized the crucial role of specific phenolic compounds in
39 the oxidative stability of VOOs, leading to the possibility of predicting the VOO oxidative stability
40 based on the concentration of these compounds.

41 **Keywords:** *Olea europaea*; phenols; antioxidants; fatty acids; vacuum; Rancimat; predictive model;
42 shelf life, malaxation, olive oil.

43 1. Introduction

44 Virgin olive oil (VOO) is the oil produced from healthy olive fruits using only mechanical methods
45 at low temperatures (typically below 28 °C) without the addition of chemical solvents. Most olive oil
46 is produced and consumed in the Mediterranean Basin, but VOO is gaining popularity worldwide due
47 to its excellent organoleptic and nutraceutical properties ^{1,2}. For this reason, increasing volumes of
48 VOO are exported yearly from traditional olive-growing countries to distant markets such as China,
49 Brazil and the United States ^{3,4}.

50 The olive oil is composed by the saponifiable and unsaponifiable fractions representing
51 respectively about 98 % and 2 % of the total weight. The saponifiable fraction is composed mainly
52 by the fatty acids, while the unsaponifiable fractions is composed by a heterogeneous complex pool
53 of minor compounds⁵. Several chemical families are included in this heterogeneous pool:
54 hydrocarbons, alcohols, sterols, volatile compounds and phenols, among others ⁶. Phenolic
55 compounds play a significant role in the VOO nutritional value and organoleptic properties, and they
56 greatly contribute to the shelf life of the product, improving its oxidative stability ⁷⁻⁹. Secoiridoids,
57 conjugated forms of hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol, are the major phenolic family in VOO, and, as in
58 the case of fatty acids ¹⁰, their concentration highly depends on the genotype¹¹.

59 The VOO phenolic profile is also dependent on the oil extraction process. Malaxation,
60 consisting of mixing olive paste to induce the coalescence of tiny oil droplets into large droplets,
61 leading to a continuous lipid phase, crucially affects the VOO phenolic composition ^{12,13}. This
62 phenomenon is because malaxation induces the activation of several endogenous fruit enzymes, such
63 as β -glucosidases and esterases, which hydrolyze precursors of oleuropein and ligstroside to produce
64 secoiridoid derivatives ¹⁴.

65 During the whole extraction process, other endogenous fruit enzymes such as phenoloxidases
66 and peroxidases become active and catalyze the oxidation of phenolic compounds, resulting in a

67 reduced phenolic concentration in VOO ¹⁵. Therefore, as a general trend, the malaxation time (MT)
68 negatively affects the concentration of major phenolic compounds found in VOO ¹⁶⁻¹⁹. However,
69 some studies have shown that the concentrations of specific phenolic compounds, such as
70 hydroxytyrosol (3,4-DHPEA), tyrosol (p-HPEA), oleocanthal (p-HPEA-EDA), ligstroside-aglycon
71 (p-HPEA-EA) and vanillin, are positively affected by MT ^{20,21}. The reason for these opposite patterns
72 remains unclear, although VOO resistance to oxidation consistently decreases with MT, and this fact
73 seems to be related to the degradation of the secoiridoid compounds ^{13,16}.

74 Few studies have evaluated the effect of oxygen (O₂) on phenolic compounds during the
75 malaxation process. The replacement of atmospheric air with inert gases such as nitrogen or carbon
76 dioxide seems to decrease enzymatic activity, preserving the VOO phenolic content, but these
77 alternatives are costly ²²⁻²⁴. The vacuum method, which removes oxygen traces, is applied to different
78 food industrial processes with the aim of preventing oxidation of the valuable natural chemical
79 compounds (such as phenols) ^{25,26}. Although some VOO extraction companies have started to apply
80 an “under vacuum extraction technology” ²⁷, no scientific studies have evaluated the significance of
81 this approach concerning the VOO phenolic profile.

82 The estimation of the VOO shelf life and the main factors influencing this parameter are
83 important to guarantee the long-term VOO quality. The Rancimat test, involving the artificial aging
84 of oil, is frequently used to determine the VOO shelf life, which usually ranges from nine to more
85 than 18 months and is mainly altered by lipid oxidation ^{28,29}. VOO resistance to oxidative
86 deterioration has been principally attributed to its fatty acid composition, with special emphasis on
87 the concentration of oleic and linoleic acids. Thus, oils that are rich in oleic acid or have a high oleic
88 acid/linoleic acid ratio tend to be more stable against oxidation than oils with a low ratio between
89 these two acids ³⁰.

90 While the relationship between the total phenolic concentration of VOO and the shelf life is
91 well supported, the effects of individual phenolic compounds in this regard remain controversial. For

92 instance, VOOs coming from different cultivars, with different phenolic profiles and concentrations,
93 have exhibited similar oxidation rates ^{16,31}. Additionally, molecules with catechol moieties, such as
94 oleuropein aglycon (3,4-DHPEA-EA) and oleacein (3,4-DHPEA-EDA), have shown a remarkable
95 resistance to oxidation ^{32,33}; but the presence of simple phenols such as hydroxytyrosol has shown the
96 opposite effect, contributing to low oxidative stability of the oils ³⁴. Therefore, it seems that the
97 distribution of phenolic compounds plays an important role in VOO oxidative stability. However,
98 there are no conclusive results as to whether the varying phenolic composition of VOO contributes
99 to determining its resistance to oxidation and its shelf life ¹⁶.

100 In this study, we evaluated the effect of MT and the absence of oxygen during malaxation in
101 the phenolic and fatty acid profiles of eight monovarietal VOOs with three goals: first, to evaluate
102 the effect of MT in the VOO phenolic and fatty acid profiles under the recommended malaxation
103 temperature, set at 28 °C; second, to evaluate the effect of vacuum conditions during malaxation on
104 the VOO composition by reducing the occurrence of undesired enzymatic and nonenzymatic
105 processes; and finally, to evaluate the extent to which the phenolic and fatty acid profiles of VOO
106 might be able to determine the oxidative stability or even predict the best before date (BBD) of VOO.

107 **2. Materials and methods**

108 **2.1. Olive cultivars and experimental design**

109 Olive fruit samples were collected during the 2017/2018 crop season from an experimental orchard
110 located at the World Olive Germplasm Bank of Cordoba (WOGB) (CAP-UCO-IFAPA), specifically
111 in the cultivar collection located at the University of Cordoba (Cordoba, Spain, 37°55'56.5" N,
112 4°43'13.3" W and 173 m above sea level). The olive trees of the collection were planted in 2011 in a
113 north-south orientation with 7 m between rows and 6 m between trees (approximately 238 trees ha⁻¹).
114 This collection included approximately 400 cultivars from 22 countries, which were identified and
115 authenticated by morphological and molecular methods ³⁵.

116 Three experiments were designed to accomplish the proposed goals of this study: the first and
117 second experiments were aimed at evaluating the influence of malaxation time and malaxation
118 atmospheric conditions (vacuum) on the phenolic profile. The third experiment evaluated the
119 prediction of the VOO oxidative stability and BBD based on its phenolic and fatty acid composition.

120 For the first experiment, we selected six cultivars showing remarkable diversity in their
121 phenolic profiles according to Miho et al. (2018): ‘Arbosana’, ‘Bosana’, ‘Blanqueta’, ‘Coratina’,
122 ‘Frantoio’ and ‘Mixani’. The VOO of these cultivars was extracted by applying three different MTs:
123 10, 30 and 60 min, where 30 min is the standard time used in the olive oil extraction process. The
124 experiment was conducted in triplicate for a total of 54 VOO analyzed samples (6 cultivars \times 3 MTs
125 \times 3 replicates = 54 samples).

126 The second experiment was focused on the analysis of the VOO samples from six different
127 cultivars: ‘Bosana’, ‘Blanqueta’, ‘Frantoio’, ‘Levantinka’, ‘Mixani’ and ‘Picual’. The selection of
128 these cultivars followed the same criteria as the first experiment, but it was also subject to the
129 availability of fruits to conduct both experiments. For this reason, four cultivars were shared by
130 experiments 1 and 2, but the other two cultivars were unique to each experiment. In experiment 2, we
131 evaluated the effect of VOO extraction under vacuum conditions versus standard conditions with
132 three replicates. In total, 36 VOO samples were analyzed (6 cultivars \times 2 extraction conditions \times 3
133 replicates = 36 samples).

134 Finally, the third experiment combined the 90 VOO samples used in the previous experiments
135 (1 and 2) to exhaustively characterize the predictive capacity and the effect of specific phenolic and
136 fatty acid profiles on the oxidative stability of the product, previously determined by the Rancimat
137 method.

138 **2.2. Olive fruit sampling and VOO extraction**

139 Two olive trees per cultivar were manually harvested by sampling all orientations within the canopy.
140 A total of 3 kg of fruit per tree was collected at ripening index (RI) 2.0 (yellowish-red in color)
141 according to the method proposed by the International Olive Oil Council ³⁶.

142 Monovarietal VOOs were obtained using an Abencor extraction system (MC2 Ingeniería y
143 Sistemas, Sevilla, Spain) under the conditions recommended by the manufacturer ³⁷. The olives were
144 crushed with a hammer mill equipped with a 4-mm sieve at 3000 rpm. The different MTs (10, 30 and
145 60 min) were tested to evaluate the influence of this parameter on the phenolic profile of VOO
146 samples.

147 Additionally, performing malaxation under vacuum was tested through the Abencor system
148 with a technical modification designed by the authors (**Figure S1**). This modification was based on
149 coupling an external pump that allowed for operation under pressurized conditions (12 psi) to
150 minimize the presence of oxygen during malaxation. The malaxation temperature was kept constant
151 at 28 °C.

152 Afterwards, the olive pomace of all treatments was centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 2 min. No
153 water was added to the pomace at any step of the process. The VOO was decanted into graduated
154 cylinders for 30 min and immediately stored in amber glass bottles at -20 °C until analysis.

155 **2.3. Reagents and standards**

156 Mass spectrometry (MS) grade methanol (MeOH) and *n*-hexane, both from Scharlab (Barcelona,
157 Spain), were used for sample preparation and chromatographic analysis. MS-grade formic acid, also
158 from Scharlab, was used as an ionization agent in the chromatographic mobile phases. For the
159 preparation of the aqueous mobile phase and the hydroalcoholic extractant mixture, deionized water
160 (18 MΩ•cm) from a Millipore Milli-Q water purification system (Bedford, MA, USA) was used.

161 Nine phenolic compounds were determined in the VOO samples: hydroxytyrosol, oleacein,
162 oleocanthal, two isomers of oleuropein aglycon, two isomers of ligstroside aglycon, luteolin and
163 apigenin. The aglycon isomers of oleuropein and ligstroside were distinguished according to their
164 chemical structures: the aldehyde open forms of oleuropein aglycon (AOleAgly, the sum of
165 stereoisomers) and the monoaldehyde closed form of the oleuropein aglycon (MAOleAgly).
166 Similarly, the aldehyde open forms of ligstroside aglycon (ALigAgly, the sum of stereoisomers) and
167 the monoaldehyde closed form of ligstroside aglycon (MALigAgly) were also discriminated ³⁸.
168 Standards for oleacein, oleocanthal, and the aldehydic open forms of oleuropein aglycon and
169 ligstroside aglycon were provided by Prof. Prokopios Magiatis of the University of Athens (Greece).
170 The purity of standards (>98%) was confirmed by LC–MS/MS. Due to the commercial unavailability
171 of the standards, the monoaldehyde forms were quantified using the corresponding standards for the
172 aldehyde open forms. The standards of hydroxytyrosol, apigenin and luteolin were purchased from
173 Extrasynthese (Genay, France).

174 Standard solutions of nonsecoiridoid phenols were prepared in methanol (1 mg/mL), while
175 secoiridoid derivatives were prepared at the same concentration in pure acetonitrile to preserve their
176 stability and avoid undesired conversion to acetal and hemiacetal derivatives.

177 **2.4. Sample preparation for the analysis of phenolic compounds**

178 The isolation of phenolic compounds from the VOO samples was conducted by liquid–liquid
179 extraction following previously published protocols ³⁹. Briefly, 1 g of VOO was mixed with 2 mL *n*-
180 hexane; then, 2 mL of 60:40 (v/v) methanol-water was added, shaken for 2 min and centrifuged for 5
181 min at 2000 rpm. The extraction was repeated once more in order to enhance the extraction efficiency
182 ⁴⁰. The resulting phenolic extracts were analyzed by triple quadrupole LC–MS/MS (Agilent
183 Technologies 6460 Triple Quad LC/MS) with three different dilution factors (1:2, 1:50 and 1:200
184 v/v) to account for concentration variability.

185 **2.5. LC-MS/MS analysis of phenolic compounds**

186 Analysis was performed by reversed-phase liquid chromatography followed by electrospray
187 ionization (ESI) in negative mode and tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS). Ten microliters of the
188 obtained extract were injected in triplicate into the LC system for chromatographic separation of the
189 target compounds using a C18 Pursuit XRs Ultra column (50×2.0 mm i.d., 2.8 μm particle size) from
190 Varian (Walnut Creek, CA, USA). The column compartment was kept at 30 °C. Mobile phase A was
191 0.1% aqueous formic acid, while mobile phase B was 0.1% formic acid in MeOH. The gradient
192 program, at a 0.4 mL/min constant flow rate, was as follows: initially, 50% phase A and 50% phase
193 B were maintained for 0.5 min; from 0.5 to 2 min, mobile phase A was decreased from 50 to 20%;
194 and from min 2 to 4, mobile phase A was decreased from 20 to 0%. This last composition was
195 maintained for 1 min. After each analysis, the column was equilibrated at starting conditions for 5
196 min.

197 The samples were monitored by MS/MS in multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode using
198 selective transitions from precursor to product ions for each analyte. The MRM parameters for the
199 analysis of target phenols are listed in **Table S1**.

200 The flow rate and temperature of the drying gas (N₂) were 10 L/min and 300 °C, respectively.
201 The nebulizer pressure was 50 psi, and the capillary voltage was 3000 V. The dwell time was set at
202 200 μs.

203 **2.6. Quantitation of the target compounds and statistical analysis**

204 Absolute quantitative analysis was performed by calibration curves obtained using refined high oleic
205 sunflower oil spiked with multistandard solutions of the target phenols. The absence of quantifiable
206 levels of phenols in the refined oil was checked by direct analysis with the developed method. Nine
207 phenolic concentrations from 0.1 ng/mL to 5 μg/mL were injected in triplicate to obtain the calibration

208 curves. The concentrations of phenols in the monovarietal VOOs were determined with these
209 calibration curves using three replicates per sample.

210 **2.7. Determination of the oxidation stability index in VOO samples**

211 The oxidation stability index was measured by the Rancimat Method using a 743 Rancimat System
212 from Metrohm (Herisau, Switzerland). The analysis was performed by heating 3.2 g of each VOO
213 sample to 100 °C with a 10 L/h air flow rate. Rancimat analyses were carried out in the Agricultural
214 and Food Laboratory of Cordoba (Cordoba, Spain), which is the reference laboratory of the Andalusia
215 Regional Government.

216 **2.8. VOO fatty acid composition analysis**

217 Determination of the fatty acid composition of VOO samples was carried out by GC–FID analysis
218 after derivatization by transesterification. The protocol was initiated by taking 0.1 g of VOO that was
219 mixed with 2 mL of n-hexane. Then, 1 mL of methanolic potassium hydroxide (0.5 mol/L was added
220 as the derivatization agent and the mixture was agitated for 1 min at 1500 × g. The processed samples
221 were allowed to rest for 10 min to permit the separation of the phases. Next, the organic phase,
222 enriched with the fatty acid methyl esters, was diluted 1:10 (v/v) prior to injection into the GC–FID
223 system (Agilent 7820A GC System). For chromatographic separation, an SPTM-2560 fused silica
224 column (100m x 0.25mm x 0.2 µm film thickness) from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA) was used as
225 the stationary phase. The injection volume was 1 µL in splitless injection mode. Helium was used as
226 the carrier gas with a 1 mL/min flow rate. The injector and detector temperatures were set at 250 °C.
227 The EZ Chrom Elite Compact (Version 3.3.2, Agilent Technologies) was employed as the acquisition
228 and data treatment software. The results were expressed in relative terms as percentages.

229 **2.9. Statistical analysis**

230 The effects of the cultivar, MT and vacuum conditions on the phenolic composition were evaluated
231 by factorial analysis of variance (ANOVA) ($p < 0.05$). Box-Cox transformation of the data was

232 applied to fit normality when appropriate. The existence of significant pairwise differences among
233 the different processing conditions for the same cultivar was evaluated by a Bonferroni post hoc test.
234 The relationship between VOO composition and oxidative stability was studied by multiple linear
235 regression analysis. To test the contribution of subsets of the independent variable to the regression
236 model, a stepwise analysis of variance of the individual variables was used⁴¹. Collinearity among
237 independent variables of the model was studied using variance inflation factors (VIFs). Subsequently,
238 the simplest model was selected, and the contribution of a subset of the independent variables to the
239 overall model was selected using an F-test of the difference between the cumulative sums of squares
240 for the model with/without each variable ⁴². To validate the regression model, the entire data set was
241 split into regression (70%) and validation (30%) by a randomly process using MS Excel (Microsoft,
242 Redmond, WA). The regression/validation process was conducted 15 times (i.e., 15 randomizations
243 of the data). A regression analysis was used to validate the model output against laboratory data
244 according to the coefficient of determination (R^2), R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom (Ra^2), and the
245 pattern of residuals over predicted and independent variables. Furthermore, principal component
246 analysis (PCA) was applied to evaluate potential association patterns between individual phenols and
247 the VOO oxidative stability measured by the Rancimat test. The statistical analyses were performed
248 using SPSS and XLSTAT software (IBM SPSS Statistics, version 23; XLSTAT v.2014.5.03,
249 Addinsoft, Paris, France).

250 **3. Results and Discussion**

251 ***3.1. Influence of malaxation time on the VOO phenolic profiles***

252 Malaxation variables (temperature and time) significantly influence the VOO phenolic profile,
253 eliciting enzymatic activity with special emphasis on β -glucosidases and esterase. β -glucosidases
254 catalyze the hydrolysis of oleuropein and ligstroside to form their aglycon forms but also contribute
255 to the formation of oleacein and oleocanthal in combination with esterase. On the other hand, an

256 excessive malaxation time negatively affects the VOO phenolic concentrations by triggering
257 undesired reactions catalyzed by oxidases and phenol-oxidases ^{12,13,15}.

258 The influence of MT on the concentration of specific phenols remains controversial ^{20,21}. In
259 our study, the malaxation temperature was held constant at 28 °C for all the treatments to control
260 oxidative reactions and to comply with the methodology optimized by Miho et al. (2018). The six
261 selected cultivars ('Arbosana', 'Blanqueta', 'Bosana', 'Coratina', 'Frantoio' and 'Mixani') were
262 characterized by diverse and contrasting VOO phenolic profiles (**Table 1**) ¹¹. The phenolic profiles
263 of VOOs extracted from 'Frantoio' and 'Mixani' showed a predisposition for the aglycon isomers to
264 dominate, while 'Arbosana', 'Blanqueta', 'Bosana' and 'Coratina' VOOs tended to be higher in
265 oleocanthal and oleacein. In line with this evidence, we hypothesized that MT could have a
266 differential effect on the phenolic profile of VOOs extracted from cultivars with various
267 predispositions.

268 According to the ANOVA statistical analyses performed, MT significantly (p -value < 0.0001)
269 affected the VOO phenolic concentration (**Table S2 and Figure S2**). As a general trend, the
270 concentration of aglycon forms decreased with MT, while the concentration of oleocanthal and
271 oleacein increased, mostly in the interval from 10 to 30 min. Afterwards, from 30 to 60 min, the
272 oleocanthal and oleacein concentrations in VOOs from all cultivars did not significantly change
273 (**Figure 1, Table S3**). The observed reduction of oleuropein and ligstroside aglycon isomers during
274 malaxation is in agreement with a previous report by Germerk and Gómez-Rico ^{20,21}. However, our
275 results further highlighted a positive effect of MT on the concentrations of oleocanthal and oleacein.
276 Thus, an increase in malaxation time from 10 to 60 min increased the oleocanthal concentration in
277 VOOs obtained from 'Coratina', 'Frantoio' and 'Mixani' cultivars by 2.2-, 1.9- and 2.7-fold,
278 respectively.

279 The sum of phenolic compounds (or total phenolic compound concentration) was also affected
280 by MT (p -value < 0.002). The maximum total phenolic concentration was achieved for MTs of 10

281 and 30 min, with no significant differences between the treatments (**Figure 1, Table S3**). In contrast,
282 the lowest total amount of phenolic compounds was observed with the longest MT (60 min), in
283 agreement with previous studies^{16,18}. ‘Arbosana’ was the exception to this trend, showing the lowest
284 phenolic concentration compared with the other cultivars. In addition, the total phenolic concentration
285 in this cultivar did not significantly change from a MT of 10 to 60 min.

286 ANOVA analysis showed that the variability of the nine target phenolic compounds was
287 highly explained by the model with R^2 values ranging from 0.670 to 0.991 ($p < 0.0001$; **Table S2**).
288 According to the eta-squared value (η^2), which explains the contribution of each factor to the observed
289 variability, the cultivar (genotype) was the most relevant factor in explaining the variability of the
290 monitored phenols. This value, η^2 , for the cultivar factor, ranged from 50.6% for hydroxytyrosol to
291 96.7% for apigenin. On the other hand, the MT factor significantly accounted for a proportion of
292 variance ranging from 1% for MALigAgly to 19.7% for ALigAgly and AOleAgly ($p < 0.05$). The
293 interaction of *cultivar* \times *MT* was only significant for oleocanthal and ALigAgly compounds, and the
294 η^2 value was always below 8%. The different transformation dynamics of phenolic compounds in
295 different cultivars during the MT justified this occasionally significant interaction. For example, the
296 oleocanthal concentration increased constantly from 10 to 60 min of MT for half of the cultivars
297 (Coratina, Frantoio, Mixani), while for the other half (Arbosana, Blanqueta, Bosana), the
298 concentration of this phenol increased from 10 to 30 min of MT but then decreased from 30 to 60
299 min.

300 **3.2. Effect of malaxation under vacuum conditions on the VOO phenolic profiles**

301 Different strategies have been proposed to minimize the oxygen content during the malaxation
302 process to preserve minor compounds that are degraded by enzymatic activity. The most common
303 approach, but not cost-effective, is the injection of inert gasses, mainly nitrogen or carbon dioxide, to
304 replace the oxygen^{22,23,43}. A potential less expensive method is to apply vacuum conditions during
305 malaxation. In this research study, we compared the effect of malaxation under vacuum and

306 atmospheric (standard) conditions in the VOO phenolic profiles of six cultivars (**Table 2**).
307 ‘Blanqueta’, ‘Bosana’, and ‘Levantinka’ VOOs were characterized by the predominance of
308 oleocanthal and oleacein, while ‘Frantoio’, ‘Mixani’ and ‘Picual’ provided VOOs enriched in aglycon
309 forms.

310 A factorial ANOVA was executed to determine the influence of malaxation under vacuum
311 conditions and elucidate the relative influence of the involved factors on the VOO phenolic profile:
312 (1) malaxation conditions (vacuum versus standard conditions); (2) cultivar (genotype); and (3) the
313 interaction between both factors. All the phenolic compounds analysed were highly and significantly
314 ($p < 0.005$) affected by the three evaluated factors with R^2 ranging from 0.832 to 0.988 (**Table S4**,
315 **Figure S3**). The cultivar contributed to explaining the highest phenolic variability, with η^2 ranging
316 from 77.4% in case of hydroxytyrosol to 98.2% for luteolin, and MALigAgly ($p < 0.0001$). The
317 malaxation conditions (vacuum/standard), also contributed significantly to explain the differences
318 found in VOO phenolic profiles (η^2 from 0.3 to 5.6%; $p < 0.05$). In this last case, the concentration of
319 most phenolic compounds was significantly increased with the application of vacuum condition
320 during the malaxation process. The exceptions to this trend were oleocanthal, luteolin and
321 MALigAgly, which increased their concentration but not significantly (**Table S5, Figure S4**). The
322 interaction between factors (cultivar \times malaxation conditions) was significant only for MaOleAgly
323 and the Phenolic Sum, with $\eta^2 = 2.3\%$ ($p = 0.012$) and $\eta^2 = 1.1\%$ ($p = 0.041$), respectively. This
324 interaction between factors occurs because the phenolic compounds are not transformed in the same
325 way for all cultivars during the extraction process. Thus, ‘Blanqueta’, ‘Frantoio’ and ‘Mixani’
326 cultivars resulted in being significantly ($p < 0.05$) richer in Phenolic Sum concentration when
327 extracted under vacuum condition, while the other cultivars did not show the same trend (**Table S5**).

328 **3.3. Contribution of the individual phenolic compounds to the VOO oxidative stability**

329 The preventive action of phenolic compounds against the oxidative deterioration of VOO has rarely
330 been investigated. Most of the previous studies focused on the influence of the fatty acid composition

331 and total phenolic content, without considering individual phenolic compounds^{16,31,32,34}. To address
332 this point, the VOO samples evaluated in both previous experiments (a total of 90 VOO samples from
333 eight olive cultivars, ‘Arbosana’, ‘Blanqueta’, ‘Bosana’, ‘Coratina’, ‘Frantoio’, ‘Levantinka’,
334 ‘Mixani’ and ‘Picual’) were merged into a unique data set (**Tables 1 and 2**). The characterization of
335 these samples was completed by analyzing their oxidative stability (Rancimat hours) and the fatty
336 acid content (**Tables S6 and S7**). With all analytical data, we ran a principal component analysis
337 (PCA) to evaluate the sample clustering and the relationships between the explanatory variables:
338 concentration of phenolic and fatty acids compounds versus the oxidative stability (Rancimat hours).
339 The first two principal components (PC1 and PC2) explained 85.3% of the variability. **Figure 2** and
340 **Tables S8 and S9** show that oxidative stability, expressed in Rancimat hours, reported a positive
341 correlation with the aglycon isomers, oleic acid and stearic acid, in agreement with previous studies
342^{30,32,33,44}. Conversely, the oxidative stability was negatively correlated with the concentrations of
343 oleocanthal, oleacein, and hydroxytyrosol as well as linoleic, linolenic, and palmitic acids. These
344 negative correlations seem to be spurious correlations due to the secondary negative correlations that
345 exist among several phenolic compounds and among several fatty acids (**Tables S8 and S9**). For
346 example, the Rancimat variable is highly positively correlated with the ALigAgly compound and
347 highly negatively correlated with oleocanthal; on the other hand, ALigAgly and oleocanthal are also
348 highly negatively correlated. Furthermore, the variable “Phenolic Sum” (or total phenolic content)
349 showed a low and nonsignificant ($p > 0.05$) correlation with the oxidative stability variable
350 (Rancimat), which illustrates that the oxidative stability is related to the concentration and
351 composition of individual phenolic compounds rather than to the total phenolic content. **Figure 2** also
352 shows the distribution of VOO samples according to their chemical profile. Clearly, the cultivars
353 marked in a red-violet color were characterized by higher oxidative stability than the cultivars marked
354 in a blue color. Therefore, the cultivars were clustered into two main groups according to their VOO
355 composition. The samples of the first group (red) were characterized by high concentrations of
356 oleuropein and ligstroside aglycon isomers and/or high concentrations of stearic and oleic acid; the

357 second group samples (blue) were rich in oleocanthal, oleacein, and hydroxytyrosol as well as
358 linoleic, linolenic, and palmitic acids.

359 According to these results, we might conclude that VOO oxidative stability highly depends
360 on the fatty acid and individual phenolic composition. To better demonstrate this effect, we defined
361 the “*f*” ratio as an indicator of the main phenols found in VOO:

$$362 \quad f = \frac{[aglycon\ forms]}{[oleocanthal] + [oleacein]}$$

363 where [*aglycon forms*] is the sum of the concentrations of all aglycon isomers of oleuropein and
364 ligstroside, and [*oleocanthal*] and [*oleacein*] are the concentrations of these phenols in the VOO
365 samples. A high *f* index value indicates that the VOO phenolic profile is predominantly composed of
366 aglycon isomers, while a low *f* index value indicates that VOO is predominantly composed of
367 oleocanthal and oleacein. Both aglycon isomers and oleocanthal-oleacein are produced from the same
368 substrates, oleuropein and ligstroside. However, aglycon isomers are produced by β -glucosidase
369 hydrolysis, while oleocanthal and oleacein are formed by the action of β -glucosidase and esterase
370 enzymes^{12,13,15}. The *f* ratio value of the analyzed samples revealed a significant correlation between
371 this parameter and VOO oxidative stability ($R^2 = 0,6824$; $p < 0,05$). This association is also
372 demonstrated in **Figure 3** as a proof of concept by dividing the total set of samples (90 samples) into
373 two groups obtained by PCA (red and blue groups). The groups were nominally defined as “less
374 stable oils” (33 samples with Rancimat response < 31 h) and “very stable oils” (57 samples with
375 Rancimat response > 44 h). Then, a relative and descriptive comparison of the parameters that might
376 be related to the oil oxidative stability was carried out between both groups. These descriptive
377 comparisons demonstrated that the total phenolic content was similar for both groups of VOOs, but
378 the individual phenolic profile was completely different, owing to the varied concentrations of
379 secoiridoids. The *f* ratio clearly shows that the individual phenolic profile of the “less stable” group
380 was completely different compared to the “very stable” group. The “less stable” group shows a low *f*

381 ratio (rich in oleocanthal and oleacein, and poor in aglycon forms), while the contrary was observed
382 for the “very stable” group. Complementarily, the oleic acid/linoleic acid ratio had higher values for
383 highly stable VOOs compared to less stable VOOs.

384 **3.4. Best before date predictive model by multiple regression analysis**

385 Subsequently, we performed a multiple linear regression analysis to determine a predictive
386 mathematical model for VOO stability (expressed in Rancimat hours) based on the phenolic and fatty
387 acid compositions. After using the stepwise selection process and checking the collinearity of the
388 phenolic compounds and fatty acids, a first linear regression was selected, in which three phenolic
389 compounds (hydroxytyrosol, oleacein, and AOleAgly) and one fatty acid (linoleic acid) were
390 considered explanatory variables of the oxidative stability. This first regression model explained
391 95.4% (R^2) of the total variance with the individual and general p -values being highly significant (p
392 < 0.0001). According to the F-test, the contribution of oleacein to the sum of squares was not
393 significant at $p = 0.08$. Subsequently, four different multiple linear regressions were conducted using
394 only three of the four independent selected variables (hydroxytyrosol, oleacein, AOleAgly, and
395 linoleic acid). The multiple linear regression using hydroxytyrosol, AOleAgly, and linoleic acid as
396 variables explained 92.3% (R^2) of the total variance with the individual and general p -values being
397 highly significant ($p < 0.0001$). After the iteration process, the selected model was Y (hours) =
398 $49.6+5.34(\text{hydroxytyrosol})+0.02(\text{AOleAgly})-1.6(\text{linoleic acid})$ (Table 3). The 15 regression lines
399 (output against analytical data) used for the validation of the multiple regression model showed an R^2
400 value > 0.909 with highly significant p -values ($p < 0.0001$). These results highlight that individual
401 phenols and fatty acids determine the oxidative stability of olive oil, introducing the possibility of
402 predicting the VOO oxidative stability based on the concentration of these compounds.

403 **Abbreviations:**

404 ALigAgly - aldehyde open forms of ligstroside aglycon, AOleAgly - aldehyde open forms of
405 oleuropein aglycon, BBD - best before date, MALigAgly - monoaldehyde closed form of ligstroside

406 aglycon, MAOleAgly - monoaldehyde closed form of the oleuropein aglycon, MS - mass
407 spectrometry, MT - malaxation time, PCA - principal component analysis, VOO - virgin olive oil.

408

409 **Chemical compounds studied in this article:** Hydroxytyrosol (PubChem CID: 82755); Oleacein
410 (3,4-DHPEA-EDA) (PubChem CID: 18684078); Oleocanthal (p-HPEA-EDA) (PubChem CID:
411 16681728); Oleuropein aglycon (3,4-DHPEA-EA) (PubChem CID: 124202093); Luteolin (PubChem
412 CID: 5280445); Apigenin (PubChem CID: 5280443).

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420

421 **Figure legends:**

422 **Figure 1.** (A) Mean differences for the main groups of phenolic compounds found in olive oil from
423 six cultivars processed at three different malaxation times. (B) Phenolic concentrations for each
424 cultivar processed at three different malaxation times. Phenolic concentrations are expressed in
425 mg/kg.

426 **Figure 2.** The loading plot (A) and scores plot (B) of the principal component analysis of olive oil
427 samples obtained from eight cultivars. PCA was done using the concentrations of phenolic
428 compounds, the fatty acid profile and oxidative stability measured by the Rancimat method as input
429 components. The color scale of scores (cultivars) represents their oxidative stability classification.
430 The violet-red cultivars tend to be much more stable than the blue cultivars.
431 **RANCIMAT** – olive oil oxidative stability expressed in hours; **Phenolic sum** – the sum of all
432 phenolic compounds analyzed; **AOleAgly** – Aldehydic open forms of oleuropein aglycon;
433 **MAOleAgly** – Monoaldehydic closed form of oleuropein aglycon; **ALigAgly** – Aldehydic open
434 forms of ligstroside aglycon; **MALigAgly** – Monoaldehydic closed form of ligstroside aglycon. **Pic**
435 – Picual, **Mix** – Mixani, **Lev** – Levantinka, **Fran** – Frantoio, **Cor** – Coratina, **Bos** – Bosana, **Blan** –
436 Blanqueta, **Arb** – Arbosana.

437 **Figure 3.** Influence of the VOO chemical composition on its oxidative stability.

438 **Supplementary figure 1.** Experimental set-up installed in the Abencor system to test the effect of
439 vacuum in the malaxation step (left) versus standard conditions (right).

440 **Supplementary figure 2.** Mean concentration of phenolic compounds in VOO from six cultivars at
441 three malaxation times.

442 **Supplementary figure 3.** Mean concentration of phenolic compounds in VOO from six cultivars
443 obtained by applying vacuum during malaxation or under atmospheric pressure.

444 **Supplementary figure 4.** A- Mean differences for the main groups of phenolic compounds found in
445 olive oil from six cultivars processed at two different malaxation conditions: under vacuum or
446 standard conditions. B- Phenolic concentrations for each cultivar processed at two different
447 malaxation conditions. Phenolic concentrations are expressed in mg/kg. (N – standard or atmospheric
448 condition; V – vacuum condition).

449 **Table legends:**

450 **Table 1.** Phenolic concentrations (expressed as mg/kg) determined in virgin olive oil from six
451 cultivars made by using the Abencor system at three malaxation times.

452 **Table 2.** Phenolic concentrations (expressed as mg/kg) determined in virgin olive oil from six
453 cultivars made by using the Abencor system under vacuum and in standard conditions (atmospheric
454 pressure).

455 **Table 3.** Multiple linear regression analysis results used to develop a predictive model using the
456 concentrations of phenolic compounds as explanatory variables to determine the oxidative stability
457 measured by the Rancimat test.

458 **Supplementary table 1.** Multiple Reaction Monitoring (MRM) parameters for quantitative analysis
459 of phenolic compounds by LC–MS/MS.

460 **Supplementary table 2.** ANOVA results for the evaluation of the influence of malaxation time and
461 genotype on the phenolic profile of virgin olive oil. The results include the R^2 coefficient (proportion
462 of variability explained by the studied factors), F-value and type III SS (type III sum of squares) for
463 the general model, while the F-value, η^2 (contribution of each factor to the observed variability) and

464 p-value are listed for each factor (cultivar and malaxation time) as well as for the interaction between
465 both factors.

466 **Supplementary table 3.** Pairwise comparisons (Bonferroni test) to analyze the differences in
467 phenolic concentrations of VOO for each cultivar at different malaxation times (10, 30 and 60 min)
468 with 95% confidence level.

469 **Supplementary table 4.** ANOVA results for the evaluation of the influence of malaxation under
470 vacuum conditions and genotype on the phenolic profile of virgin olive oil. The results include the
471 R^2 coefficient (proportion of variability explained by the studied factors), F-value and type III SS
472 (type III sum of squares) for the general model, while the F-value, η^2 (contribution of each factor to
473 the observed variability) and p-value are listed for each factor (cultivar and malaxation time) as well
474 as for the interaction between both factors.

475 **Supplementary table 5.** Pairwise comparisons (Bonferroni test) to analyse the differences in
476 phenolic concentrations of VOO for each cultivar at two different malaxation conditions (under
477 vacuum or standard conditions) with 95% confidence level.

478 **Supplementary table 6.** Concentration of the main fatty acids (expressed as %) found in virgin olive
479 oil samples for the experiment evaluating the influence of malaxation time in the phenolic profile.
480 The oxidative stability measured by the Rancimat test (expressed in hours) is also listed.

481 **Supplementary table 7.** Concentration of the main fatty acids (expressed as %) found in virgin olive
482 oil samples for the experiment evaluating the influence of vacuum during malaxation in the phenolic
483 profile. The oxidative stability measured by the Rancimat test (expressed in hours) is also listed.

484 **Supplementary table 8.** Correlation matrix (Pearson) of RANCIMAT and phenolic compounds.

485 **Supplementary table 9.** Correlation matrix (Pearson) RANCIMAT and fatty acids.

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Table 1. Phenolic concentrations (expressed as mg/kg) determined in virgin olive oil from six cultivars made by using the Abencor system at three malaxation times.

Cultivar	MT*	Hydroxytyrosol	Apigenin	Luteolin	Oleocanthal	Oleacein	MALigAgly	ALigAgly	MAOleAgly	AOleAgly	Phenolic Sum
Arbosana	10	0.71 ± 0.10	9.7 ± 0.28	8.6 ± 0.83	93.9 ± 4.0	380 ± 41.2	25.7 ± 1.5	53.5 ± 9.2	95.8 ± 12.1	52.7 ± 11.3	721 ± 67.2
Arbosana	30	0.88 ± 0.23	8.5 ± 0.1	7.0 ± 0.24	116 ± 6.8	470 ± 111	22.1 ± 1.6	25.9 ± 3.0	89.0 ± 5.6	25.3 ± 4.1	765 ± 119
Arbosana	60	1.1 ± 0.22	7.8 ± 0.16	7.0 ± 0.09	104 ± 3.2	439 ± 85.2	20.2 ± 0.28	7.2 ± 0.06	74.9 ± 6.3	14.8 ± 2.3	675 ± 96.3
Bosana	10	0.85 ± 0.19	3.0 ± 0.28	5.6 ± 0.31	140 ± 31.8	394 ± 93.6	73.5 ± 15.6	207 ± 29.3	163 ± 20.5	81.8 ± 12.7	1069 ± 162
Bosana	30	1.4 ± 0.34	2.7 ± 0.24	5.1 ± 0.66	201 ± 14.4	545 ± 9.8	73.2 ± 6.5	66.0 ± 11.9	143 ± 5.5	40.2 ± 2.7	1077 ± 15.2
Bosana	60	2.3 ± 0.63	2.3 ± 0.04	4.4 ± 0.37	184 ± 5.3	472 ± 22.1	63.6 ± 0.92	26.3 ± 4.9	119 ± 14.5	22.3 ± 2.9	896 ± 31.8
Blanqueta	10	2.3 ± 0.35	0.97 ± 0.13	4.0 ± 0.28	187 ± 11.7	1314 ± 165	36.7 ± 4.0	66.2 ± 6.7	167 ± 5.6	83.1 ± 8.4	1861 ± 147
Blanqueta	30	2.7 ± 0.24	0.87 ± 0.16	3.7 ± 0.42	199 ± 6.2	1354 ± 293	37.4 ± 1.3	24.3 ± 2.0	155 ± 7.4	38.4 ± 3.3	1815 ± 293
Blanqueta	60	2.1 ± 0.36	0.78 ± 0.11	3.3 ± 0.17	183 ± 10.5	1009 ± 227	36.1 ± 4.4	6.1 ± 0.8	125 ± 17.5	17.7 ± 3.1	1383 ± 246
Coratina	10	1.8 ± 0.20	2.2 ± 0.05	4.7 ± 0.14	109 ± 23.7	545 ± 27.8	84.3 ± 11.5	334 ± 37.7	220 ± 34.5	244 ± 24.9	1544 ± 143
Coratina	30	1.4 ± 0.14	1.7 ± 0.08	3.6 ± 0.31	206 ± 30.4	1062 ± 69.7	79.5 ± 9.9	137 ± 19.2	167 ± 36.7	101 ± 4.4	1759 ± 75.7
Coratina	60	1.5 ± 0.11	1.4 ± 0.14	2.8 ± 0.29	236 ± 28.2	1021 ± 55.7	71.8 ± 10.9	51.9 ± 7.5	140 ± 29.2	35.1 ± 5.2	1562 ± 117
Frantoio	10	1.3 ± 0.24	0.66 ± 0.07	1.6 ± 0.28	63.5 ± 11.8	321 ± 29.6	260 ± 5.3	832 ± 62.7	479 ± 74.8	762 ± 205	2720 ± 340
Frantoio	30	1 ± 0.15	0.43 ± 0.07	1.0 ± 0.09	87.3 ± 11.9	390 ± 54.3	288 ± 27.7	665 ± 116.1	417 ± 52.5	557 ± 98.7	2407 ± 329
Frantoio	60	0.91 ± 0.13	0.39 ± 0.09	0.82 ± 0.11	121 ± 24.0	415 ± 89.7	306 ± 29.4	600 ± 78.9	415 ± 80.6	431 ± 74.9	2291 ± 307
Mixani	10	0.9 ± 0.22	4.3 ± 0.36	12.2 ± 1.2	26.6 ± 5.8	218 ± 47.7	67.4 ± 2.1	301 ± 31.2	235 ± 31.8	330 ± 54.8	1195 ± 117
Mixani	30	1.2 ± 0.15	3.6 ± 0.53	10.0 ± 2.1	55.4 ± 9.3	382 ± 50.2	63.3 ± 6.1	196 ± 36.0	198 ± 18.1	226 ± 54.5	1135 ± 103
Mixani	60	0.83 ± 0.05	3.0 ± 0.26	8.1 ± 1.1	72.0 ± 9.8	327 ± 12.0	56.5 ± 4.3	114 ± 9.8	128 ± 7.0	110 ± 14.8	820 ± 37.3

*Malaxation time (min).

Table 2. Phenolic concentrations (expressed as mg/kg) determined in virgin olive oil from six cultivars made by using the Abencor system under vacuum and in standard conditions (atmospheric pressure).

Cultivar	(N-V)*	Hydroxytyrosol	Apigenin	Luteolin	Oleocanthal	Oleacein	MALigAgly	ALigAgly	MAOleAgly	AOleAgly	Phenolic Sum
Blanqueta	N	2.1 ± 0.22	1.3 ± 0.07	5.8 ± 0.01	247 ± 17.8	1621 ± 239	48.5 ± 0.9	30.1 ± 3.1	224 ± 15.9	49.6 ± 5.4	2230 ± 264
Blanqueta	V	2.7 ± 0.21	1.3 ± 0.01	5.7 ± 0.25	263 ± 3.0	1834 ± 110	49.2 ± 4.7	39.0 ± 5.0	247 ± 28.6	56.5 ± 12.0	2498 ± 145
Bosana	N	2.3 ± 0.20	4.6 ± 0.60	8.8 ± 0.97	238 ± 17.0	616 ± 69.6	85.5 ± 8.0	85.9 ± 22.1	160 ± 14.3	70.1 ± 10.0	1272 ± 112
Bosana	V	2.5 ± 0.36	4.8 ± 0.54	9.2 ± 0.73	258 ± 14.2	747 ± 83.7	89.5 ± 4.7	103 ± 37.0	176 ± 11.1	81.9 ± 19.1	1472 ± 157
Frantoio	N	0.81 ± 0.03	1.1 ± 0.19	2.4 ± 0.39	112 ± 9.1	419 ± 33.8	364 ± 25.1	1149 ± 96.2	422 ± 53.0	579 ± 92.3	3049 ± 270
Frantoio	V	1.0 ± 0.05	1.2 ± 0.12	2.7 ± 0.34	106 ± 14.8	635 ± 119	341 ± 16.8	1280 ± 55.0	598 ± 49.3	916 ± 80.4	3881 ± 246
Levantinka	N	2.0 ± 0.47	2.0 ± 0.29	10.2 ± 1.4	85.0 ± 17.5	493 ± 130	100 ± 3.9	200 ± 18.6	329 ± 16.7	177 ± 31.0	1398 ± 123
Levantinka	V	2.1 ± 0.65	2.5 ± 0.17	9.9 ± 0.83	83.7 ± 22.4	526 ± 80.0	101 ± 11.8	249 ± 26.7	361 ± 58.6	251 ± 30.8	1586 ± 144
Mixani	N	1.1 ± 0.02	7.4 ± 0.34	17.7 ± 0.89	67.1 ± 17.7	365 ± 32.0	79.4 ± 3.5	211 ± 22.5	185 ± 7.4	225 ± 32.4	1159 ± 10.7
Mixani	V	1.4 ± 0.06	7.8 ± 0.37	18.6 ± 0.77	69.2 ± 16.2	583 ± 90.2	83.9 ± 5.5	250 ± 31.1	276 ± 8.0	378 ± 50.4	1668 ± 29.6
Picual	N	2.0 ± 0.46	3.3 ± 0.26	7.8 ± 0.48	26.9 ± 5.5	110 ± 16.6	85.6 ± 6.5	271 ± 12.6	147 ± 9.1	172 ± 8.6	826 ± 45.7
Picual	V	2.3 ± 0.53	3.0 ± 0.32	7.0 ± 0.45	29.1 ± 1.3	124 ± 11.3	90.9 ± 2.0	313 ± 15.8	171 ± 5.9	214 ± 17.6	955 ± 50.1

*N: standard conditions (atmospheric pressure); V: vacuum conditions.

Table 3. Multiple linear regression analysis results used to develop a predictive model using the concentrations of phenolic compounds as explanatory variables to determine the oxidative stability measured by the Rancimat test.

Model Summary^b – phenolic and fatty acid compounds

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
				R Square Change	F Change	DF regression	Df total	Sig. F Change	
0.9609 ^a	0,9234	0,9207	2.2660	0,9234	345,64	3	89	0.000	1.368

Coefficients^a

Explanatory variables (Phenolic compounds)	Coefficient	Std. Error	T	Sig. (P)	VIF	Correlations (Dependent Variable: RANCIMAT Hours)		
						Pearson Correlation (R)	Partial	Part
(Constant)	49,603	1,44	34,46	0,0000	5			
Hydroxytyrosol	5,348	0,77	6,93	0,0000	1,5	-0.340	0.515	0.093
AOleAgly	0,029	0,00	14,89	0,0000	1,2	0.753	0.636	0.127
Linoleic C18:2	-1,625	0,08	-19,53	0,0000	1,7	-0.831	-0.670	-0.139

Mathematic model to estimate the Oxidative Stability in base of the oil phenolic and fatty acid composition:

$$\text{OS (Hours)} = (49.603) + (5.348 \cdot \text{hydroxytyrosol}) + (0.029 \cdot \text{AOleAgly}) + (-1.625 \cdot \text{Linoleic acid})$$

a. Predictors (explanatory variables): Hydroxytyrosol, AOleAgly, Linoleic C18:2.

b. Dependent Variable: Oxidative stability (OS) expressed in RANCIMAT hours.

Figure 1. (A) Mean differences for the main groups of phenolic compounds found in olive oil from six cultivars processed at three different malaxation times. (B) Phenolic concentrations for each cultivar processed at three different malaxation times. Phenolic concentrations are expressed in mg/kg.

Figure 2. The loading plot (A) and scores plot (B) of the principal component analysis of olive oil samples obtained from eight cultivars. PCA was done using the concentrations of phenolic compounds, the fatty acid profile and oxidative stability measured by the Rancimat method as input components. The color scale of scores (cultivars) represents their oxidative stability classification. The violet-red cultivars tend to be much more stable than the blue cultivars.

RANCIMAT – olive oil oxidative stability expressed in hours; **Phenolic sum** – the sum of all phenolic compounds analyzed; **AOleAgly** – Aldehydic open forms of oleuropein aglycon; **MAOleAgly** – Monoaldehydic closed form of oleuropein aglycon; **ALigAgly** – Aldehydic open forms of ligstroside aglycon; **MALigAgly** – Monoaldehydic closed form of ligstroside aglycon. **Pic** – Picual, **Mix** – Mixani, **Lev** – Levantinka, **Fran** – Frantoio, **Cor** – Coratina, **Bos** – Bosana, **Blan** – Blanqueta, **Arb** – Arbosana.

Figure 3. Influence of the VOO chemical composition on its oxidative stability.

Supplementary figure 1. Experimental set-up installed in the Abencor system to test the effect of vacuum in the malaxation step (left) versus standard conditions (right).

Supplementary figure 2. Mean concentration of phenolic compounds in VOO from six cultivars at three malaxation times.

Supplementary figure 3. Mean concentration of phenolic compounds in VOO from six cultivars obtained by applying vacuum during malaxation or under atmospheric pressure.

Supplementary figure 4. A- Mean differences for the main groups of phenolic compounds found in olive oil from six cultivars processed at two different malaxation conditions: under vacuum or standard conditions. B- Phenolic concentrations for each cultivar processed at two different malaxation conditions. Phenolic concentrations are expressed in mg/kg. (N – standard or atmospheric condition; V – vacuum condition).

Supplementary table 1. Multiple Reaction Monitoring (MRM) parameters for quantitative analysis of phenolic compounds by LC–MS/MS.

Phenolic compounds	Retention time (min)	Q1 voltage (V)	Precursor ion (<i>m/z</i>)	Collision energy (eV)	Quantitative transition (<i>m/z</i>)	Product ion confirmation (<i>m/z</i>)	
Hydroxytyrosol	2.1	110	153.1	10	153-123	108	
3,4-DHPEA-EDA (Oleacein)	4.3	110	319.1	12	319-59	139	
3,4-DHPEA-EA	AOleAgly	4.6	110	377	12	377-275	307
	MAOleAgly	5.9	110	377	12	377-275	307
p-HPEA-EDA (Oleocanthal)	5.4	110	303.1	12	303-59	137	
p-HPEA-EA	ALigAgly	5.5	110	361.1	12	361-291	101
	MALigAgly	6.2	110	361.1	12	361-291	101
Luteolin	6.3	170	285	35	285-133	175	
Apigenin	6.6	170	269	35	269-117	151	

AOleAgly – Aldehydic open forms of Oleuropein Aglycon; **MAOleAgly** – Monoaldehydic closed form of Oleuropein Aglycon.
ALigAgly – Aldehydic open forms of Ligstroside Aglycon; **MALigAgly** – Monoaldehydic closed form of Ligstroside Aglycon.

Supplementary table 2. ANOVA results for the evaluation of the influence of malaxation time and genotype on the phenolic profile of virgin olive oil. The results include the R² coefficient (proportion of variability explained by the studied factors), F-value and type III SS (type III sum of squares) for the general model, while the F-value, η^2 (contribution of each factor to the observed variability) and p-value are listed for each factor (cultivar and malaxation time) as well as for the interaction between both factors.

Parameter	Hydroxytyrosol	Apigenin	Luteolin	Oleocanthal	Oleacein	MALigAgly	ALigAgly	MAOleAgly	AOleAgly	Phenolic Sum	
<i>R</i> ²	0.691	0.991	0.979	0.955	0.670	0.963	0.988	0.832	0.966	0.830	
<i>F</i>	4.730	226.385	98.877	45.123	4.300	55.025	174.758	10.523	60.347	10.320	
Type III SS	6.339	50.876	92.935	10558.825	33.259	1.817	264.02	19.058	20.769	5.702	
<i>p</i> -value	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	
Cultivar	<i>F</i>	11.790	750.996	317.006	121.978	12.626	184.255	456.124	29.846	154.918	31.378
	η^2 (%)	50.6	96.7	92.3	75.9	57.9	94.8	75.8	69.4	72.9	74.2
	<i>p</i> -value	< 0.0001									
Malaxation time	<i>F</i>	0.892	40.333	39.946	47.516	2.903	4.857	296.056	9.505	104.593	7.775
	η^2 (%)	1.5	2.1	4.7	11.8	5.3	1.0	19.7	8.8	19.7	7.4
	<i>p</i> -value	0.419	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.068	0.014	< 0.0001	0.0009	< 0.0001	0.002
Cultivar× MT	<i>F</i>	1.968	1.290	1.599	6.217	0.417	0.443	9.816	1.065	4.212	0.300
	η^2 (%)	16.9	0.3	0.9	7.7	3.8	0.5	3.3	5.0	4.0	1.4
	<i>p</i> -value	0.067	0.272	0.147	< 0.0001	0.929	0.915	< 0.0001	0.413	0.001	0.977
Error	η^2 (%)	30.9	0.9	2.1	4.5	33.0	3.7	1.2	16.8	3.4	17.0
	Type III SS	2.838	0.476	1.990	495.535	16.378	0.070	3.199	3.835	0.729	1.170

Supplementary table 3. Pairwise comparisons (Bonferroni test) to analyze the differences in phenolic concentrations of VOO for each cultivar at different malaxation times (10, 30 and 60 min) with 95% confidence level.

Dependent Variable	Cultivar	(I) MT	(J) MT	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Hydroxytyrosol	Arbosana	10.0	30.0	-0,173	0,294	1,000	-0,911	0,565
			60.0	-0,344	0,294	0,749	-1,082	0,394
		30.0	10.0	0,173	0,294	1,000	-0,565	0,911
			60.0	-0,171	0,294	1,000	-0,908	0,567
		60.0	10.0	0,344	0,294	0,749	-0,394	1,082
			30.0	0,171	0,294	1,000	-0,567	0,908
	Blanqueta	10.0	30.0	-0,376	0,294	0,627	-1,114	0,362
			60.0	0,243	0,294	1,000	-0,495	0,981
		30.0	10.0	0,376	0,294	0,627	-0,362	1,114
			60.0	0,619	0,294	0,126	-0,119	1,357
		60.0	10.0	-0,243	0,294	1,000	-0,981	0,495
			30.0	-0,619	0,294	0,126	-1,357	0,119
	Bosana	10.0	30.0	-0,546	0,294	0,213	-1,284	0,192
			60.0	-0,824*	0,294	0,024	-1,562	-0,086
		30.0	10.0	0,546	0,294	0,213	-0,192	1,284
			60.0	-0,278	0,294	1,000	-1,016	0,460
		60.0	10.0	0,824*	0,294	0,024	0,086	1,562
			30.0	0,278	0,294	1,000	-0,460	1,016
	Coratina	10.0	30.0	0,398	0,294	0,552	-0,340	1,136
			60.0	0,602	0,294	0,143	-0,136	1,340
		30.0	10.0	-0,398	0,294	0,552	-1,136	0,340
			60.0	0,204	0,294	1,000	-0,534	0,942
		60.0	10.0	-0,602	0,294	0,143	-1,340	0,136
			30.0	-0,204	0,294	1,000	-0,942	0,534
	Frantoio	10.0	30.0	0,299	0,294	0,947	-0,439	1,037
			60.0	0,387	0,294	0,589	-0,351	1,125
		30.0	10.0	-0,299	0,294	0,947	-1,037	0,439
			60.0	0,088	0,294	1,000	-0,650	0,826
		60.0	10.0	-0,387	0,294	0,589	-1,125	0,351
			30.0	-0,088	0,294	1,000	-0,826	0,650
	Mixani	10.0	30.0	0,076	0,294	1,000	-0,662	0,814
			60.0	0,412	0,294	0,509	-0,326	1,150
		30.0	10.0	-0,076	0,294	1,000	-0,814	0,662
			60.0	0,336	0,294	0,781	-0,402	1,074
		60.0	10.0	-0,412	0,294	0,509	-1,150	0,326
			30.0	-0,336	0,294	0,781	-1,074	0,402

*Significant at 95% confidence level. ^a Adjustment for multiple comparisons by Bonferroni test.

Dependent Variable	Cultivar	(I) MT	(J) MT	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Lower Bound
Apigenin	Arbosana	10.0	30.0	1,212*	0,176	0,000	0,770	1,654
			60.0	1,865*	0,176	0,000	1,423	2,307
		30.0	10.0	-1,212*	0,176	0,000	-1,654	-0,770
			60.0	0,653*	0,176	0,002	0,211	1,095
		60.0	10.0	-1,865*	0,176	0,000	-2,307	-1,423
			30.0	-0,653*	0,176	0,002	-1,095	-0,211
	Blanqueta	10.0	30.0	0,097	0,176	1,000	-0,345	0,540
			60.0	0,184	0,176	0,906	-0,258	0,627
		30.0	10.0	-0,097	0,176	1,000	-0,540	0,345
			60.0	0,087	0,176	1,000	-0,355	0,529
		60.0	10.0	-0,184	0,176	0,906	-0,627	0,258
			30.0	-0,087	0,176	1,000	-0,529	0,355
	Bosana	10.0	30.0	0,363	0,176	0,140	-0,079	0,805
			60.0	0,720*	0,176	0,001	0,278	1,162
		30.0	10.0	-0,363	0,176	0,140	-0,805	0,079
			60.0	0,357	0,176	0,151	-0,085	0,799
		60.0	10.0	-0,720*	0,176	0,001	-1,162	-0,278
			30.0	-0,357	0,176	0,151	-0,799	0,085
	Coratina	10.0	30.0	0,471*	0,176	0,034	0,029	0,913
			60.0	0,761*	0,176	0,000	0,319	1,203
		30.0	10.0	-0,471*	0,176	0,034	-0,913	-0,029
			60.0	0,290	0,176	0,325	-0,152	0,732
		60.0	10.0	-0,761*	0,176	0,000	-1,203	-0,319
			30.0	-0,290	0,176	0,325	-0,732	0,152
	Frantoio	10.0	30.0	0,236	0,176	0,564	-0,206	0,678
			60.0	0,273	0,176	0,391	-0,170	0,715
		30.0	10.0	-0,236	0,176	0,564	-0,678	0,206
			60.0	0,036	0,176	1,000	-0,406	0,479
		60.0	10.0	-0,273	0,176	0,391	-0,715	0,170
			30.0	-0,036	0,176	1,000	-0,479	0,406
	Mixani	10.0	30.0	0,654*	0,176	0,002	0,211	1,096
			60.0	1,241*	0,176	0,000	0,799	1,683
		30.0	10.0	-0,654*	0,176	0,002	-1,096	-0,211
			60.0	0,588*	0,176	0,006	0,145	1,030
		60.0	10.0	-1,241*	0,176	0,000	-1,683	-0,799
			30.0	-0,588*	0,176	0,006	-1,030	-0,145

*Significant at 95% confidence level. ^aAdjustment for multiple comparisons by Bonferroni test.

Dependent Variable	Cultivar	(I) MT	(J) MT	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Lower Bound
Luteolin	Arbosana	10.0	30.0	1,629*	0,577	0,023	0,180	3,078
			60.0	1,609*	0,577	0,025	0,160	3,058
		30.0	10.0	-1,629*	0,577	0,023	-3,078	-0,180
			60.0	-0,020	0,577	1,000	-1,469	1,429
		60.0	10.0	-1,609*	0,577	0,025	-3,058	-0,160
			30.0	0,020	0,577	1,000	-1,429	1,469
	Blanqueta	10.0	30.0	0,297	0,577	1,000	-1,152	1,746
			60.0	0,688	0,577	0,723	-0,761	2,137
		30.0	10.0	-0,297	0,577	1,000	-1,746	1,152
			60.0	0,390	0,577	1,000	-1,058	1,839
		60.0	10.0	-0,688	0,577	0,723	-2,137	0,761
			30.0	-0,390	0,577	1,000	-1,839	1,058
	Bosana	10.0	30.0	0,502	0,577	1,000	-0,946	1,951
			60.0	1,187	0,577	0,141	-0,262	2,636
		30.0	10.0	-0,502	0,577	1,000	-1,951	0,946
			60.0	0,684	0,577	0,730	-0,765	2,133
		60.0	10.0	-1,187	0,577	0,141	-2,636	0,262
			30.0	-0,684	0,577	0,730	-2,133	0,765
	Coratina	10.0	30.0	1,087	0,577	0,203	-0,362	2,536
			60.0	1,829*	0,577	0,009	0,380	3,278
		30.0	10.0	-1,087	0,577	0,203	-2,536	0,362
			60.0	0,742	0,577	0,620	-0,707	2,191
		60.0	10.0	-1,829*	0,577	0,009	-3,278	-0,380
			30.0	-0,742	0,577	0,620	-2,191	0,707
	Frantoio	10.0	30.0	0,566	0,577	1,000	-0,883	2,015
			60.0	0,742	0,577	0,621	-0,707	2,190
		30.0	10.0	-0,566	0,577	1,000	-2,015	0,883
			60.0	0,176	0,577	1,000	-1,273	1,624
		60.0	10.0	-0,742	0,577	0,621	-2,190	0,707
			30.0	-0,176	0,577	1,000	-1,624	1,273
	Mixani	10.0	30.0	2,287*	0,577	0,001	0,838	3,736
			60.0	4,151*	0,577	0,000	2,702	5,600
		30.0	10.0	-2,287*	0,577	0,001	-3,736	-0,838
			60.0	1,864*	0,577	0,008	0,415	3,313
		60.0	10.0	-4,151*	0,577	0,000	-5,600	-2,702
			30.0	-1,864*	0,577	0,008	-3,313	-0,415

*Significant at 95% confidence level. a-Adjustment for multiple comparisons by Bonferroni test.

Dependent Variable	Cultivar	(I) MT	(J) MT	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Lower Bound
Oleocanthal	Arbosana	10.0	30.0	-22,125	13,553	0,334	-56,158	11,908
			60.0	-9,661	13,553	1,000	-43,694	24,372
		30.0	10.0	22,125	13,553	0,334	-11,908	56,158
			60.0	12,464	13,553	1,000	-21,569	46,497
		60.0	10.0	9,661	13,553	1,000	-24,372	43,694
			30.0	-12,464	13,553	1,000	-46,497	21,569
	Blanqueta	10.0	30.0	-11,797	13,553	1,000	-45,830	22,237
			60.0	4,533	13,553	1,000	-29,500	38,566
		30.0	10.0	11,797	13,553	1,000	-22,237	45,830
			60.0	16,330	13,553	0,708	-17,704	50,363
		60.0	10.0	-4,533	13,553	1,000	-38,566	29,500
			30.0	-16,330	13,553	0,708	-50,363	17,704
	Bosana	10.0	30.0	-61,163*	13,553	0,000	-95,196	-27,130
			60.0	-44,355*	13,553	0,007	-78,389	-10,322
		30.0	10.0	61,163*	13,553	0,000	27,130	95,196
			60.0	16,807	13,553	0,669	-17,226	50,841
		60.0	10.0	44,355*	13,553	0,007	10,322	78,389
			30.0	-16,807	13,553	0,669	-50,841	17,226
	Coratina	10.0	30.0	-96,787*	13,553	0,000	-130,821	-62,754
			60.0	-127,132*	13,553	0,000	-161,165	-93,098
		30.0	10.0	96,787*	13,553	0,000	62,754	130,821
			60.0	-30,344	13,553	0,094	-64,378	3,689
		60.0	10.0	127,132*	13,553	0,000	93,098	161,165
			30.0	30,344	13,553	0,094	-3,689	64,378
	Frantoio	10.0	30.0	-23,776	13,553	0,264	-57,809	10,258
			60.0	-57,064*	13,553	0,000	-91,097	-23,031
		30.0	10.0	23,776	13,553	0,264	-10,258	57,809
			60.0	-33,288	13,553	0,057	-67,321	0,745
		60.0	10.0	57,064*	13,553	0,000	23,031	91,097
			30.0	33,288	13,553	0,057	-0,745	67,321
	Mixani	10.0	30.0	-28,799	13,553	0,122	-62,832	5,235
			60.0	-45,371*	13,553	0,006	-79,404	-11,337
		30.0	10.0	28,799	13,553	0,122	-5,235	62,832
			60.0	-16,572	13,553	0,688	-50,605	17,461
		60.0	10.0	45,371*	13,553	0,006	11,337	79,404
			30.0	16,572	13,553	0,688	-17,461	50,605

*Significant at 95% confidence level. ^a-Adjustment for multiple comparisons by Bonferroni test.

Dependent Variable	Cultivar	(I) MT	(J) MT	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Lower Bound
Oleacein	Arbosana	10.0	30.0	-90,072	156,248	1,000	-482,417	302,273
			60.0	-58,671	156,248	1,000	-451,016	333,674
		30.0	10.0	90,072	156,248	1,000	-302,273	482,417
			60.0	31,401	156,248	1,000	-360,944	423,746
		60.0	10.0	58,671	156,248	1,000	-333,674	451,016
			30.0	-31,401	156,248	1,000	-423,746	360,944
	Blanqueta	10.0	30.0	-40,120	156,248	1,000	-432,465	352,225
			60.0	304,870	156,248	0,177	-87,475	697,215
		30.0	10.0	40,120	156,248	1,000	-352,225	432,465
			60.0	344,990	156,248	0,101	-47,355	737,335
		60.0	10.0	-304,870	156,248	0,177	-697,215	87,475
			30.0	-344,990	156,248	0,101	-737,335	47,355
	Bosana	10.0	30.0	-150,443	156,248	1,000	-542,788	241,902
			60.0	-11,034	156,248	1,000	-403,379	381,311
		30.0	10.0	150,443	156,248	1,000	-241,902	542,788
			60.0	139,409	156,248	1,000	-252,936	531,754
		60.0	10.0	11,034	156,248	1,000	-381,311	403,379
			30.0	-139,409	156,248	1,000	-531,754	252,936
	Coratina	10.0	30.0	-383,359	156,248	0,057	-775,704	8,986
			60.0	-175,869	156,248	0,803	-568,214	216,477
		30.0	10.0	383,359	156,248	0,057	-8,986	775,704
			60.0	207,490	156,248	0,578	-184,855	599,836
		60.0	10.0	175,869	156,248	0,803	-216,477	568,214
			30.0	-207,490	156,248	0,578	-599,836	184,855
	Frantoio	10.0	30.0	-69,524	156,248	1,000	-461,870	322,821
			60.0	-28,170	156,248	1,000	-420,515	364,175
		30.0	10.0	69,524	156,248	1,000	-322,821	461,870
			60.0	41,355	156,248	1,000	-350,990	433,700
		60.0	10.0	28,170	156,248	1,000	-364,175	420,515
			30.0	-41,355	156,248	1,000	-433,700	350,990
	Mixani	10.0	30.0	-164,020	156,248	0,903	-556,365	228,325
			60.0	-109,510	156,248	1,000	-501,855	282,835
		30.0	10.0	164,020	156,248	0,903	-228,325	556,365
			60.0	54,510	156,248	1,000	-337,835	446,855
		60.0	10.0	109,510	156,248	1,000	-282,835	501,855
			30.0	-54,510	156,248	1,000	-446,855	337,835

*Significant at 95% confidence level. ^a-Adjustment for multiple comparisons by Bonferroni test.

Dependent Variable	Cultivar	(I) MT	(J) MT	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Lower Bound
MALigAgly	Arbosana	10.0	30.0	3,599	27,778	1,000	-66,153	73,350
			60.0	5,449	27,778	1,000	-64,302	75,200
		30.0	10.0	-3,599	27,778	1,000	-73,350	66,153
			60.0	1,850	27,778	1,000	-67,901	71,602
		60.0	10.0	-5,449	27,778	1,000	-75,200	64,302
			30.0	-1,850	27,778	1,000	-71,602	67,901
	Blanqueta	10.0	30.0	-0,703	27,778	1,000	-70,454	69,048
			60.0	0,552	27,778	1,000	-69,199	70,303
		30.0	10.0	0,703	27,778	1,000	-69,048	70,454
			60.0	1,255	27,778	1,000	-68,496	71,006
		60.0	10.0	-0,552	27,778	1,000	-70,303	69,199
			30.0	-1,255	27,778	1,000	-71,006	68,496
	Bosana	10.0	30.0	0,302	27,778	1,000	-69,449	70,053
			60.0	9,975	27,778	1,000	-59,776	79,727
		30.0	10.0	-0,302	27,778	1,000	-70,053	69,449
			60.0	9,674	27,778	1,000	-60,078	79,425
		60.0	10.0	-9,975	27,778	1,000	-79,727	59,776
			30.0	-9,674	27,778	1,000	-79,425	60,078
	Coratina	10.0	30.0	4,823	27,778	1,000	-64,929	74,574
			60.0	12,426	27,778	1,000	-57,325	82,177
		30.0	10.0	-4,823	27,778	1,000	-74,574	64,929
			60.0	7,603	27,778	1,000	-62,148	77,354
		60.0	10.0	-12,426	27,778	1,000	-82,177	57,325
			30.0	-7,603	27,778	1,000	-77,354	62,148
	Frantoio	10.0	30.0	-28,594	27,778	0,930	-98,345	41,157
			60.0	20,558	27,778	1,000	-49,194	90,309
		30.0	10.0	28,594	27,778	0,930	-41,157	98,345
			60.0	49,152	27,778	0,256	-20,599	118,903
		60.0	10.0	-20,558	27,778	1,000	-90,309	49,194
			30.0	-49,152	27,778	0,256	-118,903	20,599
Mixani	10.0	30.0	4,065	27,778	1,000	-65,686	73,816	
		60.0	10,896	27,778	1,000	-58,855	80,647	
	30.0	10.0	-4,065	27,778	1,000	-73,816	65,686	
		60.0	6,831	27,778	1,000	-62,920	76,582	
	60.0	10.0	-10,896	27,778	1,000	-80,647	58,855	
		30.0	-6,831	27,778	1,000	-76,582	62,920	

*Significant at 95% confidence level. ^a-Adjustment for multiple comparisons by Bonferroni test.

Dependent Variable	Cultivar	(I) MT	(J) MT	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Lower Bound
ALigAgly	Arbosana	10.0	30.0	30,952	32,812	1,000	-51,440	113,344
			60.0	47,705	32,812	0,464	-34,688	130,097
		30.0	10.0	-30,952	32,812	1,000	-113,344	51,440
			60.0	16,753	32,812	1,000	-65,640	99,145
		60.0	10.0	-47,705	32,812	0,464	-130,097	34,688
			30.0	-16,753	32,812	1,000	-99,145	65,640
	Blanqueta	10.0	30.0	41,857	32,812	0,631	-40,536	124,249
			60.0	58,457	32,812	0,250	-23,935	140,850
		30.0	10.0	-41,857	32,812	0,631	-124,249	40,536
			60.0	16,601	32,812	1,000	-65,792	98,993
		60.0	10.0	-58,457	32,812	0,250	-140,850	23,935
			30.0	-16,601	32,812	1,000	-98,993	65,792
	Bosana	10.0	30.0	140,563*	32,812	0,000	58,171	222,956
			60.0	183,628*	32,812	0,000	101,236	266,021
		30.0	10.0	-140,563*	32,812	0,000	-222,956	-58,171
			60.0	43,065	32,812	0,593	-39,328	125,457
		60.0	10.0	-183,628*	32,812	0,000	-266,021	-101,236
			30.0	-43,065	32,812	0,593	-125,457	39,328
	Coratina	10.0	30.0	196,389*	32,812	0,000	113,997	278,782
			60.0	281,677*	32,812	0,000	199,284	364,069
		30.0	10.0	-196,389*	32,812	0,000	-278,782	-113,997
			60.0	85,287*	32,812	0,040	2,895	167,680
		60.0	10.0	-281,677*	32,812	0,000	-364,069	-199,284
			30.0	-85,287*	32,812	0,040	-167,680	-2,895
	Frantoio	10.0	30.0	166,332*	32,812	0,000	83,940	248,725
			60.0	231,406*	32,812	0,000	149,013	313,798
		30.0	10.0	-166,332*	32,812	0,000	-248,725	-83,940
			60.0	65,074	32,812	0,165	-17,319	147,466
		60.0	10.0	-231,406*	32,812	0,000	-313,798	-149,013
			30.0	-65,074	32,812	0,165	-147,466	17,319
Mixani	10.0	30.0	105,507*	32,812	0,008	23,115	187,900	
		60.0	187,822*	32,812	0,000	105,429	270,214	
	30.0	10.0	-105,507*	32,812	0,008	-187,900	-23,115	
		60.0	82,314	32,812	0,050	-0,078	164,707	
	60.0	10.0	-187,822*	32,812	0,000	-270,214	-105,429	
		30.0	-82,314	32,812	0,050	-164,707	0,078	

*Significant at 95% confidence level. ^a-Adjustment for multiple comparisons by Bonferroni test.

Dependent Variable	Cultivar	(I) MT	(J) MT	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Lower Bound
MAOleAgly	Arbosana	10.0	30.0	6,860	36,768	1,000	-85,465	99,186
			60.0	20,937	36,768	1,000	-71,389	113,263
		30.0	10.0	-6,860	36,768	1,000	-99,186	85,465
			60.0	14,077	36,768	1,000	-78,249	106,402
		60.0	10.0	-20,937	36,768	1,000	-113,263	71,389
			30.0	-14,077	36,768	1,000	-106,402	78,249
	Blanqueta	10.0	30.0	12,195	36,768	1,000	-80,131	104,521
			60.0	41,876	36,768	0,787	-50,449	134,202
		30.0	10.0	-12,195	36,768	1,000	-104,521	80,131
			60.0	29,681	36,768	1,000	-62,644	122,007
		60.0	10.0	-41,876	36,768	0,787	-134,202	50,449
			30.0	-29,681	36,768	1,000	-122,007	62,644
	Bosana	10.0	30.0	-12,919	36,768	1,000	-105,245	79,407
			60.0	10,680	36,768	1,000	-81,645	103,006
		30.0	10.0	12,919	36,768	1,000	-79,407	105,245
			60.0	23,600	36,768	1,000	-68,726	115,925
		60.0	10.0	-10,680	36,768	1,000	-103,006	81,645
			30.0	-23,600	36,768	1,000	-115,925	68,726
	Coratina	10.0	30.0	52,484	36,768	0,486	-39,841	144,810
			60.0	112,870*	36,768	0,012	20,545	205,196
		30.0	10.0	-52,484	36,768	0,486	-144,810	39,841
			60.0	60,386	36,768	0,328	-31,940	152,712
		60.0	10.0	-112,870*	36,768	0,012	-205,196	-20,545
			30.0	-60,386	36,768	0,328	-152,712	31,940
	Frantoio	10.0	30.0	62,355	36,768	0,296	-29,971	154,680
			60.0	97,251*	36,768	0,036	4,925	189,576
		30.0	10.0	-62,355	36,768	0,296	-154,680	29,971
			60.0	34,896	36,768	1,000	-57,430	127,222
		60.0	10.0	-97,251*	36,768	0,036	-189,576	-4,925
			30.0	-34,896	36,768	1,000	-127,222	57,430
Mixani	10.0	30.0	36,093	36,768	0,998	-56,233	128,419	
		60.0	106,017*	36,768	0,020	13,691	198,343	
	30.0	10.0	-36,093	36,768	0,998	-128,419	56,233	
		60.0	69,924	36,768	0,196	-22,402	162,250	
	60.0	10.0	-106,017*	36,768	0,020	-198,343	-13,691	
		30.0	-69,924	36,768	0,196	-162,250	22,402	

*Significant at 95% confidence level. ^a-Adjustment for multiple comparisons by Bonferroni test.

Dependent Variable	Cultivar	(I) MT	(J) MT	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Lower Bound
AOleAgly	Arbosana	10.0	30.0	20,812	49,504	1,000	-103,495	145,120
			60.0	31,251	49,504	1,000	-93,056	155,559
		30.0	10.0	-20,812	49,504	1,000	-145,120	103,495
			60.0	10,439	49,504	1,000	-113,868	134,746
		60.0	10.0	-31,251	49,504	1,000	-155,559	93,056
			30.0	-10,439	49,504	1,000	-134,746	113,868
	Blanqueta	10.0	30.0	44,732	49,504	1,000	-79,575	169,040
			60.0	65,404	49,504	0,584	-58,904	189,711
		30.0	10.0	-44,732	49,504	1,000	-169,040	79,575
			60.0	20,671	49,504	1,000	-103,636	144,979
		60.0	10.0	-65,404	49,504	0,584	-189,711	58,904
			30.0	-20,671	49,504	1,000	-144,979	103,636
	Bosana	10.0	30.0	28,680	49,504	1,000	-95,627	152,988
			60.0	46,485	49,504	1,000	-77,822	170,793
		30.0	10.0	-28,680	49,504	1,000	-152,988	95,627
			60.0	17,805	49,504	1,000	-106,502	142,112
		60.0	10.0	-46,485	49,504	1,000	-170,793	77,822
			30.0	-17,805	49,504	1,000	-142,112	106,502
	Coratina	10.0	30.0	156,525*	49,504	0,010	32,217	280,832
			60.0	215,391*	49,504	0,000	91,084	339,699
		30.0	10.0	-156,525*	49,504	0,010	-280,832	-32,217
			60.0	58,867	49,504	0,727	-65,441	183,174
		60.0	10.0	-215,391*	49,504	0,000	-339,699	-91,084
			30.0	-58,867	49,504	0,727	-183,174	65,441
	Frantoio	10.0	30.0	204,704*	49,504	0,001	80,397	329,011
			60.0	330,354*	49,504	0,000	206,046	454,661
		30.0	10.0	-204,704*	49,504	0,001	-329,011	-80,397
			60.0	125,649*	49,504	0,047	1,342	249,957
		60.0	10.0	-330,354*	49,504	0,000	-454,661	-206,046
			30.0	-125,649*	49,504	0,047	-249,957	-1,342
Mixani	10.0	30.0	104,652	49,504	0,125	-19,655	228,960	
		60.0	220,265*	49,504	0,000	95,958	344,572	
	30.0	10.0	-104,652	49,504	0,125	-228,960	19,655	
		60.0	115,613	49,504	0,076	-8,695	239,920	
	60.0	10.0	-220,265*	49,504	0,000	-344,572	-95,958	
		30.0	-115,613	49,504	0,076	-239,920	8,695	

*Significant at 95% confidence level. ^a-Adjustment for multiple comparisons by Bonferroni test.

Dependent Variable	Cultivar	(I) MT	(J) MT	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Lower Bound
Phenolic Sum	Arbosana	10.0	30.0	-47,306	230,318	1,000	-625,644	531,032
			60.0	40,140	230,318	1,000	-538,198	618,478
		30.0	10.0	47,306	230,318	1,000	-531,032	625,644
			60.0	87,446	230,318	1,000	-490,892	665,784
		60.0	10.0	-40,140	230,318	1,000	-618,478	538,198
			30.0	-87,446	230,318	1,000	-665,784	490,892
	Blanqueta	10.0	30.0	46,183	230,318	1,000	-532,155	624,521
			60.0	476,808	230,318	,137	-101,531	1055,146
		30.0	10.0	-46,183	230,318	1,000	-624,521	532,155
			60.0	430,625	230,318	,209	-147,713	1008,963
		60.0	10.0	-476,808	230,318	,137	-1055,146	101,531
			30.0	-430,625	230,318	,209	-1008,963	147,713
	Bosana	10.0	30.0	-54,660	230,318	1,000	-632,999	523,678
			60.0	196,462	230,318	1,000	-381,876	774,800
		30.0	10.0	54,660	230,318	1,000	-523,678	632,999
			60.0	251,122	230,318	,848	-327,216	829,461
		60.0	10.0	-196,462	230,318	1,000	-774,800	381,876
			30.0	-251,122	230,318	,848	-829,461	327,216
	Coratina	10.0	30.0	-67,970	230,318	1,000	-646,308	510,369
			60.0	322,556	230,318	,510	-255,782	900,894
		30.0	10.0	67,970	230,318	1,000	-510,369	646,308
			60.0	390,526	230,318	,296	-187,812	968,864
		60.0	10.0	-322,556	230,318	,510	-900,894	255,782
			30.0	-390,526	230,318	,296	-968,864	187,812
	Frantoio	10.0	30.0	312,598	230,318	,549	-265,740	890,936
			60.0	595,735*	230,318	,042	17,397	1174,074
		30.0	10.0	-312,598	230,318	,549	-890,936	265,740
			60.0	283,137	230,318	,681	-295,201	861,476
		60.0	10.0	-595,735*	230,318	,042	-1174,074	-17,397
			30.0	-283,137	230,318	,681	-861,476	295,201
	Mixani	10.0	30.0	60,515	230,318	1,000	-517,823	638,854
			60.0	375,923	230,318	,334	-202,415	954,261
		30.0	10.0	-60,515	230,318	1,000	-638,854	517,823
			60.0	315,407	230,318	,538	-262,931	893,746
		60.0	10.0	-375,923	230,318	,334	-954,261	202,415
			30.0	-315,407	230,318	,538	-893,746	262,931

*Significant at 95% confidence level. ^a Adjustment for multiple comparisons by Bonferroni test.

Supplementary table 4. ANOVA results for the evaluation of the influence of malaxation under vacuum conditions and genotype on the phenolic profile of virgin olive oil. The results include the R² coefficient (proportion of variability explained by the studied factors), F-value and type III SS (type III sum of squares) for the general model, while the F-value, η^2 (contribution of each factor to the observed variability) and p-value are listed for each factor (cultivar and malaxation time) as well as for the interaction between both factors.

Parameter	Hydroxytyrosol	Apigenin	Luteolin	Oleocanthal	Oleacein	MALigAgly	ALigAgly	MAOleAgly	AOleAgly	Phenolic Sum	
<i>R</i> ²	0.832	0.985	0.985	0.974	0.978	0.984	0.988	0.970	0.980	0.981	
<i>F</i>	10.822	140.528	145.978	80.609	96.599	137.897	172.619	71.632	107.447	110.140	
Type III SS	10.405	13.012	42.319	153.953	218.978	0.005	39.687	0.001	12.48	0.017	
<i>p</i> -value	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	
Cultivar	<i>F</i>	22.135	306.440	320.126	177.022	206.016	302.764	377.123	144.739	228.272	227.976
	$\eta^2(\%)$	77.4	97.6	98.2	97.2	94.8	98.2	98.1	89.1	94.6	92.3
	<i>p</i> -value	< 0.0001									
Vacuum	<i>F</i>	6.419	4.440	0.127	0.390	23.293	1.371	12.233	45.535	33.301	57.812
	$\eta^2(\%)$	4.5	0.3	0.0	0.0	2.1	0.1	0.6	5.6	2.8	4.7
	<i>p</i> -value	0.018	0.046	0.724	0.538	< 0.0001	0.253	0.002	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Cultivar× vacuum	<i>F</i>	0.389	1.833	1.000	0.240	1.843	0.336	0.193	3.744	1.451	2.769
	$\eta^2(\%)$	1.4	0.6	0.3	0.1	0.8	0.1	0.1	2.3	0.6	1.1
	<i>p</i> -value	0.851	0.144	0.439	0.941	0.142	0.886	0.962	0.012	0.242	0.041
Error	$\eta^2(\%)$	16.8	1.5	1.5	2.6	2.2	1.6	1.2	3.0	2.0	1.9
	Type III SS	2.098	0.202	0.633	4.167	4.946	0.000	0.502	0.000	0.253	0.000

Supplementary table 5. Pairwise comparisons (Bonferroni test) to analyse the differences in phenolic concentrations of VOO for each cultivar at two different malaxation conditions (under vacuum or standard conditions) with 95% confidence level.

Dependent variable	Cultivar	(I) Condition	(J) Condition	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Hydroxytyrosol	Blanqueta	V	N	0.592*	0.280	0.045	0.014	1.169
	Bosana	V	N	0.157	0.280	0.579	-0.420	0.735
	Frantoio	V	N	0.193	0.280	0.498	-0.385	0.770
	Levantinka	V	N	0.098	0.280	0.729	-0.479	0.676
	Mixani	V	N	0.311	0.280	0.277	-0.266	0.889
	Picual	V	N	0.329	0.280	0.251	-0.248	0.907
Apigenin	Blanqueta	V	N	0.059	0.263	0.824	-0.484	0.602
	Bosana	V	N	0.174	0.263	0.514	-0.369	0.717
	Frantoio	V	N	0.132	0.263	0.619	-0.411	0.675
	Levantinka	V	N	0.541	0.263	0.051	-0.002	1.084
	Mixani	V	N	0.389	0.263	0.153	-0.154	0.932
	Picual	V	N	-0.279	0.263	0.300	-0.822	0.264
Luteolin	Blanqueta	V	N	-0.104	0.594	0.862	-1.331	1.123
	Bosana	V	N	0.391	0.594	0.517	-0.836	1.618
	Frantoio	V	N	0.334	0.594	0.579	-0.893	1.561
	Levantinka	V	N	-0.292	0.594	0.628	-1.519	0.935
	Mixani	V	N	0.878	0.594	0.152	-0.348	2.105
	Picual	V	N	-0.730	0.594	0.231	-1.957	0.497
Oleocanthal	Blanqueta	V	N	15.707	11.857	0.198	-8.766	40.179
	Bosana	V	N	19.665	11.857	0.110	-4.808	44.137
	Frantoio	V	N	-5.846	11.857	0.626	-30.318	18.626
	Levantinka	V	N	-1.365	11.857	0.909	-25.837	23.108
	Mixani	V	N	2.118	11.857	0.860	-22.355	26.590
	Picual	V	N	2.229	11.857	0.852	-22.244	26.701
Oleacein	Blanqueta	V	N	213.545*	84.631	0.019	38.875	388.215
	Bosana	V	N	131.389	84.631	0.134	-43.281	306.059
	Frantoio	V	N	215.625*	84.631	0.018	40.955	390.295
	Levantinka	V	N	33.047	84.631	0.700	-141.623	207.718
	Mixani	V	N	217.938*	84.631	0.017	43.268	392.609
	Picual	V	N	14.196	84.631	0.868	-160.474	188.867
MALigAgly	Blanqueta	V	N	0.749	8.392	0.930	-16.571	18.069
	Bosana	V	N	3.949	8.392	0.642	-13.371	21.270
	Frantoio	V	N	-22.444*	8.392	0.013	-39.764	-5.124
	Levantinka	V	N	0.845	8.392	0.921	-16.475	18.165
	Mixani	V	N	4.501	8.392	0.597	-12.819	21.821
	Picual	V	N	5.292	8.392	0.534	-12.028	22.612
ALigAgly	Blanqueta	V	N	8.834	30.835	0.777	-54.807	72.474
	Bosana	V	N	16.664	30.835	0.594	-46.977	80.305
	Frantoio	V	N	130.672*	30.835	0.000	67.031	194.313
	Levantinka	V	N	48.859	30.835	0.126	-14.781	112.500
	Mixani	V	N	39.596	30.835	0.211	-24.045	103.237
	Picual	V	N	41.762	30.835	0.188	-21.879	105.403

Dependent variable	Cultivar	(I) Condition	(J) Condition	Mean Difference (I-J)	Standard error	Sig.*	95% Confidence interval ^a	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
MAOleAgly	Blanqueta	V	N	22.391	24.244	0.365	-27.646	72.429
	Bosana	V	N	16.185	24.244	0.511	-33.853	66.222
	Frantoio	V	N	176.595*	24.244	0.000	126.557	226.632
	Levantinka	V	N	31.889	24.244	0.201	-18.148	81.927
	Mixani	V	N	90.770*	24.244	0.001	40.733	140.808
	Picual	V	N	23.658	24.244	0.339	-26.379	73.696
AOleAgly	Blanqueta	V	N	6.941	34.567	0.843	-64.401	78.283
	Bosana	V	N	11.791	34.567	0.736	-59.551	83.133
	Frantoio	V	N	336.840*	34.567	0.000	265.497	408.182
	Levantinka	V	N	74.133*	34.567	0.042	2.791	145.475
	Mixani	V	N	152.877*	34.567	0.000	81.535	224.219
	Picual	V	N	42.288	34.567	0.233	-29.054	113.630
Phenolic Sum	Blanqueta	V	N	268.713*	129.687	0.049	1.053	536.373
	Bosana	V	N	200.365	129.687	0.135	-67.295	468.025
	Frantoio	V	N	832.101*	129.687	0.000	564.441	1099.761
	Levantinka	V	N	187.757	129.687	0.161	-79.903	455.417
	Mixani	V	N	509.379*	129.687	0.001	241.719	777.038
	Picual	V	N	128.746	129.687	0.331	-138.914	396.406

*Significant at 95% confidence level. ^aAdjustment for multiple comparisons by Bonferroni test.

Supplementary table 6. Concentration of the main fatty acids (expressed as %) found in virgin olive oil samples for the experiment evaluating the influence of malaxation time in the phenolic profile. The oxidative stability measured by the Rancimat test (expressed in hours) is also listed.

Cultivar	MT*	Palmitic acid C16:0	Stearic acid C18:0	Oleic acid C18:1	Linoleic acid C18:2	Linolenic acid C18:3	Rancimat test
Arbosana	10 min	14.4 ± 0.07	2.1 ± 0.01	66.5 ± 0.32	8.9 ± 0.27	0.81 ± 0.01	38.4 ± 2.0
Arbosana	30 min	14.5 ± 0.05	2.1 ± 0.03	66.5 ± 0.32	8.8 ± 0.14	0.8 ± 0.02	43.0 ± 4.4
Arbosana	60 min	14.4 ± 0.13	2.1 ± 0.01	66.5 ± 0.20	8.9 ± 0.22	0.8 ± 0.02	44.9 ± 2.4
Bosana	10 min	15.3 ± 0.06	2.2 ± 0.01	51.9 ± 0.45	19.4 ± 0.27	1.0 ± 0.01	19.7 ± 1.8
Bosana	30 min	15.4 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.01	52.3 ± 0.43	19.6 ± 0.28	1.0 ± 0.01	23.2 ± 2.4
Bosana	60 min	15.5 ± 0.09	2.2 ± 0.01	51.9 ± 0.26	19.7 ± 0.22	1.0 ± 0.02	23.8 ± 3.4
Blanqueta	10 min	19.2 ± 0.12	1.8 ± 0.01	42.2 ± 0.39	25.8 ± 0.34	0.89 ± 0.01	24.3 ± 0.51
Blanqueta	30 min	19.1 ± 0.11	1.8 ± 0.02	42.6 ± 0.27	26.0 ± 0.23	0.89 ± 0.01	26.9 ± 1.1
Blanqueta	60 min	19.1 ± 0.10	1.8 ± 0.01	42.2 ± 0.89	26.2 ± 0.62	0.91 ± 0.03	24.0 ± 1.8
Coratina	10 min	12.9 ± 0.18	3.0 ± 0.04	64.0 ± 0.15	11.1 ± 0.12	0.95 ± 0.02	45.9 ± 1.0
Coratina	30 min	12.8 ± 0.04	3.0 ± 0.03	64.2 ± 0.13	11.1 ± 0.15	0.94 ± 0.01	44.2 ± 5.1
Coratina	60 min	12.7 ± 0.11	3.0 ± 0.03	64.0 ± 0.45	11.0 ± 0.28	0.93 ± 0.01	43.9 ± 1.3
Frantoio	10 min	13.7 ± 0.18	2.7 ± 0.08	66.5 ± 0.63	9.8 ± 0.36	0.89 ± 0.01	61.0 ± 6.0
Frantoio	30 min	13.6 ± 0.17	2.7 ± 0.05	66.6 ± 0.57	9.8 ± 0.42	0.89 ± 0.01	57.3 ± 4.6
Frantoio	60 min	13.6 ± 0.33	2.7 ± 0.02	66.4 ± 0.56	9.7 ± 0.35	0.88 ± 0.02	56.3 ± 3.2
Mixani	10 min	11.9 ± 0.08	3.0 ± 0.04	65.2 ± 0.12	11.2 ± 0.16	0.63 ± 0.01	45.5 ± 4.0
Mixani	30 min	11.8 ± 0.08	3.0 ± 0.06	64.7 ± 0.70	11.2 ± 0.13	0.63 ± 0.01	45.1 ± 1.8
Mixani	60 min	12.1 ± 0.10	3.0 ± 0.02	65.2 ± 0.08	11.4 ± 0.06	0.64 ± 0.01	39.2 ± 2.0

*Malaxation time.

Supplementary table 7. Concentration of the main fatty acids (expressed as %) found in virgin olive oil samples for the experiment evaluating the influence of vacuum during malaxation in the phenolic profile. The oxidative stability measured by the Rancimat test (expressed in hours) is also listed.

Cultivar	(N-V)*	Palmitic acid C16:0	Stearic acid C18:0	Oleic acid C18:1	Linoleic acid C18:2	Linolenic acid C18:3	Rancimat test
Blanqueta	N	19.6 ± 0.08	1.8 ± 0.02	42.4 ± 0.45	25.9 ± 0.37	0.85 ± 0.02	25.6 ± 1.1
Blanqueta	V	19.8 ± 0.02	1.7 ± 0.04	42.4 ± 0.64	26.0 ± 0.15	0.94 ± 0.02	25.8 ± 0.35
Bosana	N	15.7 ± 0.03	2.2 ± 0.02	52.5 ± 0.44	19.6 ± 0.21	1.1 ± 0.01	26.0 ± 1.3
Bosana	V	15.9 ± 0.21	2.2 ± 0.01	52.8 ± 0.31	19.6 ± 0.35	1.1 ± 0.02	26.8 ± 1.7
Frantoio	N	14.0 ± 0.14	2.7 ± 0.05	66.0 ± 0.17	9.7 ± 0.24	1.17 ± 0.29	56.3 ± 3.3
Frantoio	V	14.0 ± 0.06	2.7 ± 0.03	66.3 ± 0.31	10.0 ± 0.14	0.87 ± 0.02	66.7 ± 1.6
Levantinka	N	13.0 ± 0.10	2.8 ± 0.06	55.6 ± 0.10	20.3 ± 0.21	0.71 ± 0.03	29.6 ± 3.8
Levantinka	V	12.8 ± 0.06	2.8 ± 0.18	55.5 ± 0.38	20.1 ± 0.18	0.92 ± 0.21	31.5 ± 3.3
Mixani	N	12.5 ± 0.08	3.1 ± 0.06	65.9 ± 0.13	11.5 ± 0.08	0.69 ± 0.01	45.1 ± 1.4
Mixani	V	12.3 ± 0.09	3.1 ± 0.02	65.6 ± 0.28	11.4 ± 0.11	0.67 ± 0.01	53.4 ± 0.89
Picual	N	13.5 ± 0.36	2.3 ± 0.02	66.3 ± 0.78	5.8 ± 0.07	0.87 ± 0.02	56.2 ± 2.2
Picual	V	13.6 ± 0.15	2.3 ± 0.01	66.2 ± 0.14	5.8 ± 0.15	0.87 ± 0.01	61.0 ± 1.5

*Malaxation under vacuum (V) or standard conditions (N).

Supplementary table 8. Correlation matrix of RANCIMAT and phenolic compounds (Pearson).

Variables	RANCIMAT (h)	Hydroxytyrosol	Apigenin	Luteolin	Oleocanthal	Oleacein	MALigAgly	ALigAgly	MAOleAgly	AOleAgly	Phenolic Sum
RANCIMAT (h)	1	-0,485	0,037	-0,047	-0,658	-0,507	0,616	0,711	0,529	0,750	0,352
Hydroxytyrosol	-0,485	1	-0,315	-0,025	0,515	0,554	-0,361	-0,409	-0,209	-0,396	-0,016
Apigenin	0,037	-0,315	1	0,697	-0,270	-0,354	-0,439	-0,344	-0,461	-0,283	-0,587
Luteolin	-0,047	-0,025	0,697	1	-0,338	-0,244	-0,427	-0,318	-0,255	-0,180	-0,451
Oleocanthal	-0,658	0,515	-0,270	-0,338	1	0,789	-0,230	-0,384	-0,253	-0,467	0,160
Oleacein	-0,507	0,554	-0,354	-0,244	0,789	1	-0,268	-0,330	-0,106	-0,338	0,341
MALigAgly	0,616	-0,361	-0,439	-0,427	-0,230	-0,268	1	0,943	0,884	0,883	0,774
ALigAgly	0,711	-0,409	-0,344	-0,318	-0,384	-0,330	0,943	1	0,883	0,949	0,762
MAOleAgly	0,529	-0,209	-0,461	-0,255	-0,253	-0,106	0,884	0,883	1	0,918	0,854
AOleAgly	0,750	-0,396	-0,283	-0,180	-0,467	-0,338	0,883	0,949	0,918	1	0,743
Phenolic Sum	0,352	-0,016	-0,587	-0,451	0,160	0,341	0,774	0,762	0,854	0,743	1

Values in bold are different from 0 with a significance level $\alpha=0,05$

Supplementary table 9. RANCIMAT and fatty acids correlation matrix (Pearson).

Variables	RANCIMAT (h)	Palmitic C16:0	Stearic C18:0	Oleic C18:1	Linoleic C18:2	Linolenic C18:3
RANCIMAT (h)	1	-0,6165	0,5389	0,8383	-0,8589	-0,2421
Palmitic C16:0	-0,6165	1	-0,8933	-0,8813	0,8023	0,3975
Stearic C18:0	0,5389	-0,8933	1	0,7013	-0,5830	-0,3752
Oleic C18:1	0,8383	-0,8813	0,7013	1	-0,9777	-0,3336
Linoleic C18:2	-0,8589	0,8023	-0,5830	-0,9777	1	0,2741
Linolenic C18:3	-0,2421	0,3975	-0,3752	-0,3336	0,2741	1

Values in bold are different from 0 with a significance level $\alpha=0,05$